

Enhancing Wireless Communications via Orbital Angular Momentum Schemes enabled by Reconfigurable Holographic Metasurfaces

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Abstract—This paper studies finite-aperture holographic metasurfaces and provides a methodology to accurately evaluate and shape their electromagnetic response in terms of the scattered wavefront. Special focus is given to the use of vortex beams, carrying orbital angular momentum (OAM), with detailed analysis on transformation between plane-wave beams and vortex beams for non-trivial cases of oblique incidence in combination with wavefront shaping, i.e., steering and focusing. The results demonstrate that properly tuned reconfigurable holographic metasurfaces can effectively support multiple variable-order OAM beams, wavefront shaping and de/multiplexing, establishing their potential for future wireless communication systems and offering a promising pathway toward high-efficiency, secure, and high-capacity communications.

Index Terms—Metasurface, orbital angular momentum (OAM), vortex beams, scattering, finite aperture, physical optics

I. INTRODUCTION

The wireless communication traffic has increased significantly in the last decade. At the same time, future networks promise wider coverage, higher data rates, and introduction of new services, for example, autonomous driving, augmented/virtual reality, smart cities and internet of things, remote sensing, monitoring etc., leading to an exponential increase in data transmission [1], [2]. To address the challenges posed by these data-hungry emerging applications, researchers

have proposed several novel approaches in network architecture and communication techniques, such as the use of intelligent metasurfaces, which are expected to play a significant role in future communication systems [3]. Another emerging concept with promising potential is the use of orbital angular momentum (OAM) in wireless communication [4], although its practical implementation remains an open research area. The integration of these technologies, either individually or in combination, may enable the development of communication environments capable of meeting the stringent requirements of future networks, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Metasurfaces (MS) have emerged as a central focus in electromagnetic research [1], [5]. MSs are ultra-thin periodic composite structures consisting of sub-wavelength resonant scatterers that can interact with waves in ways not found in ordinary materials [6]. By precisely tailoring the geometry of the cells, e.g. the shape of the scatterers, their distance, their orientation and the materials used, one can control electromagnetic wave characteristics such as the amplitude, phase, and polarization. Recent advances in MS include real-time and dynamic control of each individual cell, to incorporate multiple functionalities without modifying the geometry [7]. This progress has given rise to reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS), particularly in microwave regime when tunable elements, such as varactor diodes, varistors or transistors, are

Fig. 1. Conceptual illustration of MS and OAM enabling smart environments in next-generation wireless communication systems.

used. Depending on the design, MSs can reflect, absorb, or refract incident waves – the latter is commonly referred to as Huygens metasurface [8]. Although unit cell-level analysis inherently assumes infinite periodic repetition of the same cell in both lateral dimensions, practical scenarios involve MSs with finite dimensions, which introduce diffraction, similar to a finite-diameter lens [9]. These effects are difficult to model effectively in full-wave simulations (FWS), i.e., they significantly increase the computation time and resources. Several techniques have been used to predict the behavior of finite-aperture MSs, with the most known of them being physical/Fourier optics [9].

Orbital angular momentum (OAM) is another promising scheme considered for the next generation of communication systems [10]. OAM is a physical property of non planar electromagnetic waves in which their phase twists in a helical form as they propagate, and a field-null is situated at the beam center; for this reason, OAM beams are also called vortex beams. Like all finite-extend beams, OAM beams also diffract (expand) with propagation [11], [12]. As demonstrated in [13], OAM waves can be used for wireless communications. The key advantage of OAM waves is the orthogonality of its theoretically infinite modes, which can be used to multiplex multiple signals, similar to dual-polarization schemes (which, however, supports only two modes, e.g., linear TE and TM), secure communications and overall higher efficiency [14]. Various components have been developed to produce OAM vortex beams. Some examples of them are spiral phase plates, parabolic reflector antennas, uniform circular arrays, and MSs [14].

In this work, we investigate the generation and manipulation of OAM beams using finite aperture MSs. We present the theoretical framework for computing the scattered fields as well as for generating and de/multiplexing of OAM beams. The study includes transformations from plane waves to OAM vortices and vice versa, extending the analysis to non-trivial scenarios such as oblique illumination. These techniques enable for accurate prediction of MS behavior without relying on time-consuming FWS. The novelty of this work lies in combining unit-cell level full-wave electromagnetic simulations and physical optics techniques into a semi-analytical frame-

work for predicting of the near-field scattering from finite-aperture holographic metasurfaces. Although communication-level metrics are not calculated in this work, the studied RIS-enabled OAM generation and de/multiplexing capabilities are expected to improve spectral utilization/efficiency, link reliability, and physical-layer security.

This paper is organized as follows: In Section II, we present the methodology and conditions for scattered field prediction, including field coupling within the MS, and the fundamentals of OAM beam generation using MSs under both normal and oblique incidence scenarios. In Section III, the proposed theory is applied to demonstrate various examples of plane wave to/from OAM transformation. In Section IV, we briefly compare the proposed device and methodology against related work and discuss its limitations. Finally, in Section V, we summarize the contributions of this work towards enhancing future wireless communications with RIS-enabled OAM-based schemes.

II. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

A. Analysis of Finite Aperture MS using Physical Optics

The electromagnetic behavior of a MS can be numerically analyzed using commercial FWS software, e.g. Ansys HFSS, CST studio, COMSOL, etc. For an efficient and fast simulation of the response of a MS, it is common to use Floquet boundary conditions. These conditions take advantage of the Floquet theorem to reduce the computation load supposing that the dimensions of the MS are infinite, i.e., the same cell is repeated. However, when modeling finite-aperture MS, no such condition can be applied leading to higher computational cost, if one needs to model large-aperture with FWS. Consequently, alternative analytical techniques are required to accurately and efficiently analyze finite-aperture MSs.

A valid approach is the implementation of physical/Fourier optics. Specifically, the problem can be formulated similarly to the diffraction from a square shaped lens that is placed in an aperture of an infinite opaque screen; this approximation is valid when the incident wave illuminates the MS uniformly. The same technique is used to estimate the reflected field from a fully reflective MS by invoking Babinet's principle. The aperture-diffracted lens problem has been extensively studied [9], leading to the modified Fresnel-Kirchhoff diffraction equation that can be applied to MS analysis [15].

$$E_{\text{scat}}(\vec{r}_p) = \frac{1}{j\lambda} \iint_{MS} E_{\text{int}} \cdot \Psi \cdot \frac{e^{jk d_{ps}}}{d_{ps}} dx dy, \quad (1)$$

where E_{scat} is the scattered scalar field in (V/m), $\vec{r}_p = (x_p, y_p, z_p)$ is any point at the observation plane, E_{int} is the interaction field, i.e., the field scattered from each cell after its interaction with the incident wave, d_{ps} is the Euclidean distance between \vec{r}_p and each MS cell, and Ψ is the obliquity factor calculated as

$$\Psi(\theta_{\text{inc}}, \theta_{\text{scat}}) = 0.5(\cos \theta_{\text{inc}} + \cos \theta_{\text{scat}}), \quad (2)$$

where θ_{inc} and θ_{scat} are the incident and scattering angles, the latter depending on \vec{r}_p and the cell coordinates. This equation

is used when the observation plane is distant from the MS by at least a few wavelengths.

An alternative way to express Eq. (1) is in terms of the spherical angles θ and φ for very large distances, i.e., in the radiative far-field. The resulting equation is

$$E_{\text{scat}}(\theta, \varphi) = \iint_{MS} E_{\text{int}} \psi(\theta_{\text{inc}}) \psi(\theta) \exp[j\Phi(\theta, \varphi)] dx dy, \quad (3)$$

where E_{scat} is the scattered field (now in $V \cdot m$), E_{int} is the interaction field, $\Phi(\theta, \varphi) = k \sin \theta (x \cos \varphi + y \sin \varphi) + \varphi_0$, $\psi(\theta) \approx \cos \theta$, φ and θ are the observation angles, and θ_{inc} is the angle of incidence. Eq. (3) is known as the Huygens-Fresnel formula [9]. We repeat that, in both equations, E_{int} corresponds to the local scattered field right after the interaction of the incident field with a MS unit cell, treated as an isolated scatterer.

To evaluate the E_{int} we will assume scalar approximation, i.e., the electric field will be linearly polarized (e.g., TE), so that it can be approximated by

$$E_{\text{int}} = \Gamma E_{\text{inc}}, \quad (4)$$

where Γ denotes the complex reflection coefficient introduced by the MS. Due to the discrete structure of the MS, the interaction field can be accurately computed only when the adjacent unit cells are not coupled. In such cases, E_{int} primarily arises from the local response of each unit cell to the incident field, allowing for a simplified decoupled analysis. This is important because the local response of each unit cell can be approximated using the response of an infinite MS configured with the same unit cell geometry. This approach enables the separate design of each unit cell to achieve a desired electromagnetic behavior, i.e., tuning the cell parameters so that the infinite-array configuration exhibits the required phase profile. In passive MSs, this is accomplished by matching the desired phase response through the physical geometry of the unit cell. In contrast, for RIS, the appropriate phase response is achieved by applying suitable biasing to the embedded tunable components [16].

Due to the discrete nature of the MSs, these equations can be sampled and used to predict the scattered field at an observation plane. However, a key limitation of these formulations is the computational cost associated with the evaluation of integral expressions, which can become significant if the number of unit cells increases. To reduce this complexity, the Fresnel approximation is employed. In this paper, the simplification is demonstrated for Eq. (1); however, the same approach can also be applied to Eq. (3).

For the Fresnel approximation, we will assume that the observation plane is at a distance not far from the MS but this distance is much larger than the wavelength and, at the same time, large enough to neglect the curvature of the wavefront. This results in the simplification of the term d_{ps} in Eq. (1) as $d_{\text{pd}} \approx z_p$ and

$$e^{jk d_{\text{ps}}} \approx e^{j \frac{k}{z_p} [1+0.5((x-x_p)^2+(y-y_p)^2)]}, \quad (5)$$

for the denominator and phase term respectively. Each point in the observation plane is denoted as $\vec{r}_p = (x_p, y_p, z_p)$, each MS point as $\vec{r} = (x, y, 0)$ assuming that these points are located at $z = 0$ plane. However, it is important to note that this placement is not restrictive; the MS and the observation plane can be located at arbitrary positions, provided that multiple scattering effects, including shadowing, can be neglected. With proper mathematical manipulations, Eq. (1) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{scat}}(\vec{r}_p) &= A(\vec{r}_p) \iint E_{\text{int}} \Psi e^{j \frac{k}{2z_p} (x^2+y^2)} e^{-j(\frac{kx_p}{z_p}x + \frac{ky_p}{z_p}y)} dx dy \\ &= A(\vec{r}_p) \mathcal{F}\{E_{\text{int}} \Psi e^{j \frac{k}{2z_p} (x^2+y^2)}\} |_{(x_t, y_t)}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $A(\vec{r}_p) = \frac{1}{j\lambda z_p} e^{-jkz_p} e^{-j \frac{k}{2z_p} (x_p^2+y_p^2)}$, and $x_t = \frac{kx_p}{z_p}$ and $y_t = \frac{ky_p}{z_p}$ are spatial frequencies. In Eq. (6), the field is derived using the two-dimensional Fourier transform of the term $E_{\text{int}} \Psi e^{j \frac{k}{2z_p} (x^2+y^2)}$ for each point of the observation plane. Modern fast Fourier transform (FFT) techniques enable efficient computation of the resulting field distribution. Finally, by applying the Fraunhofer approximation, we can neglect the quadratic phase terms, leading to the analytical calculation of the observed field, if E_{int} is known on the MS.

B. Vortex Beam Order Conversion using MSs

The orbital angular momentum in electromagnetic waves has been studied extensively. In [12], it is shown that a solution of the partial wave equation problem, is an electric field distribution of the form (in cylindrical coordinate system):

$$E_{\ell,p}(\rho, \varphi, z) = A_0 \frac{1}{w} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}r}{w} \right)^{|\ell|} e^{-\frac{r^2}{w^2}} L_{\ell,p} \left(\frac{2r^2}{w^2} \right) e^{j\ell\varphi} e^{j\Phi_0}, \quad (7)$$

and

$$\Phi_0 = \frac{zkw^2r}{2(z+z_r)} + (2p + |\ell| + 1) \arctan\left(\frac{z}{z_r}\right), \quad (8)$$

where ℓ and p are the azimuth and radial mode orders, respectively, $w = w(z) = 2m\lambda \frac{z}{\pi D}$ is the Gaussian spot size with m being the beam quality (typically $m \approx 1$), and D is the diameter of the aperture. In addition, $z_r = \pi \frac{w(z)}{\lambda}$ is the Rayleigh distance, A_0 is the field amplitude, and $L_{\ell,p}(x)$ is the Laguerre polynomial. This field distribution is called Laguerre–Gaussian (LG) beam and it is proven to carry orbital angular momentum [11]. The above function is commonly used to represent ideal OAM beams of different azimuth- and radial-order modes. Typically, the radial order p is set to zero while the azimuthal order ℓ (also referred to as ‘topological charge’) assumes positive or negative integer values; the value $\ell = 0$ corresponds to the fundamental Gaussian beam. This theoretical description of LG beams provides the foundation for understanding and designing practical OAM-based systems. In particular, the azimuthal phase term $e^{j\ell\varphi}$ found in Eq. (7) serves as the basis for the phase profile required to generate OAM modes using MS.

Indeed, a core functionality of an OAM-based communication systems employing MSs is the bidirectional conversion

between a plane wave and a vortex beam, under both normal and oblique incidence. To generate such a vortex beam, the phase profile, imparted by each unit cell, must reproduce the azimuthally varying phase of Eq. (7). Specifically, the required phase distribution is given by:

$$\Phi(x, y) = \ell \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) \quad (9)$$

where (x, y) are the coordinates of a point in the MS aperture, typically ‘‘sampled’’ at the center of each unit cell. Conversely, to transform an incoming OAM beam back to a planar wavefront, the MS must apply the opposite phase profile of the corresponding incident OAM beam; that is $-\Phi(x, y)$.

In addition to vortex beam generation, a practical MS must be capable of steering the waves toward arbitrary directions. This functionality can be achieved through diffraction grating theory. To redirect an incident wave under oblique illumination, unit cells are grouped into larger structures known as supercells, with dimensions larger than the wavelength [16]. These supercells support higher-order diffraction modes, allowing for precise control over the scattering direction beyond the limitations of simple phase gradient methods. The number of unit cells N within a supercell is determined by the diffraction grating equation:

$$\sin \theta_{\text{scat}} - \sin \theta_{\text{inc}} = m \left(\frac{\lambda}{ND} \right), \quad (10)$$

where D is the unit cell size, θ_{scat} is the desired scattering angle, θ_{inc} is the incidence angle, integer m is the diffraction order, and λ is the wavelength. Within each supercell, the phase of the unit cells must vary linearly to direct the wave toward the desired direction, assuming that the decoupled cell approximation holds.

To enable simultaneous vortex beam generation, directional control, and any other wavefront transformation, the MS must combine all the individual phase profiles. The total phase response in this case is the superposition of the phase that corresponds to OAM component, the phase for the beam steering and any phase profile for distinct additional functionalities such as focusing etc.

Finally, the MS phase profile can also be engineered to demultiplex multiple OAM beams received simultaneously. As demonstrated in [17], the orthogonality of OAM modes allows the MS to transform incoming vortex beams into planar wavefronts and steer them in distinct directions based on their azimuthal mode indices [18]. To achieve this, the MS phase profile must be designed as a superposition of the individual profiles required to demodulate and steer each mode into its corresponding direction, as described in [17]. This angular separation enables mode-specific routing and identification, allowing simultaneous decoding of multiple OAM channels. Additional signal processing may then be applied to extract the data carried by each individual mode.

Fig. 2. (a) The geometric parameters of the studied cells at 6 GHz are: $D \approx \lambda/8$, $g \approx D/62$, $w_p = D - g$, $\epsilon_r = 2.2$, $\tan \delta = 0.0009$, $w_L = 0.5w_p$ and $h \approx \lambda/50$. (b) Coupling between adjacent cell with square patches shape for 1×1 and 2×1 configurations. (c) Tuning of reflection phase when lumped capacitance is changed, for the 2×1 cell, at the operating frequency of $f = 6$ GHz and for $R = 1 \Omega$. The FWS were done with CST studio

III. RESULTS

A. Unit Cell Analysis

The coupling between adjacent cells is determined by the structure’s geometry and the configuration between the unit cells. For simplicity, we assume square patches as the pattern of the MS; however, the shape may vary depending on the design. For this experiment, two configurations are evaluated: the 1×1 cell structure and the 2×1 cell structure, both lying on a PEC-backed dielectric substrate. The 1×1 cell structure consists of a grid that contains square patches connected with lumped elements in one or two directions. The 2×1 cell structure comprises pairs of patches connected by a lumped element. To estimate the coupling between adjacent cells, the lumped elements will be replaced with lumped ports, and the ‘transmission’ coefficient between the two ports, one at each cell, will be measured.

The studied cell coupling geometries are depicted in Fig. 2(a) and the parameter values are given in the caption. As illustrated in Fig. 2 (b), the 1×1 cell structure exhibits significant coupling between adjacent cells because the ‘transmission’ coefficient exceeds -3 dB, while the transmission coefficient of 2×1 cell structure is below -10 dB at frequencies below 6.5 GHz, which signal minimum coupling. Finally, for the configuration of each individual 2×1 cell of the metasurface, we present in Fig. 2(c) the reflection phase at 6 GHz when the series capacitance is varied from 0 to 6 pF, e.g., by applying a DC bias voltage to a varactor diode; a parasitic series resistance of $R = 1 \Omega$ is assumed which does not affect the reflection magnitude (not shown). It is evident that the MS can achieve a wide range exceeding 270 degrees.

Fig. 3. Generation of four OAM modes ($\ell = 0, +1, +2, +3$) using the Laguerre–Gaussian Beam (LGB) model, and comparison with the scattered field from a finite aperture MS consisting of 60×60 unit cells. The scattered field is evaluated at a distance $d = 40\lambda$ from the MS. As insets at the top right of LGB panels, the phase profiles corresponding to the generation of OAM modes with $\ell = +1, +2, +3$ are shown. Diffraction effects arising from the finite aperture of the MS are evident in the generated field.

Fig. 4. Generation of an OAM vortex with topological charge $\ell = +1$, steered toward the direction $\theta_{\text{scat}} = 30^\circ$, is demonstrated under oblique plane wave illumination at $\theta = 50^\circ$ by a MS consisting of 60×60 unit cells. (a) illustrates the scattering pattern and the corresponding phase profile applied to the MS. (b) and (c) show the near-field distribution of the electric field computed using Eq. (1), while (d) presents the far-field angular distribution obtained from Eq. (3).

B. OAM Generation and OAM to plane wave Transformation

Based on the previous analysis, we then designed a MS operating at $f = 6$ GHz, composed of a 2×2 unit cell configuration. This structure is an extension of the 2×1 unit cell layout along one lateral axis, with each unit cell having a size of $D = \lambda/8$. This configuration is used in all subsequent case studies presented in this work.

In Fig. 3, to evaluate the performance of the OAM beams generated by the MS, we compare the resulting scattered field distributions with the ideal theoretical profiles described by the Laguerre–Gaussian beam model in Eq. (7). The first four OAM modes generated using LG beams are compared with the scattered fields produced by a finite aperture MS. The results indicate that the beams generated by the MS closely resemble those derived from analytical solutions. Moreover, diffraction effects arising from the finite dimensions of the MS are visible in the scattering patterns. In the Fig. 3 panels, the top right insets correspond to the phase profile applied to the MS cells for the generation of the respective OAM modes.

In Fig. 4, we examine the case of generating an OAM vortex

Fig. 5. Generation and reception of an OAM vortex beam of order $\ell = +1$ are demonstrated. In (a), the schematic and corresponding phase profiles of the MSs are shown. (b) and (c) depict the OAM beam generated by the first MS, steered at an angle $\theta_{\text{scat}} = 30^\circ$, just before it reaches the second MS. (d) and (e) illustrate the transformation of the OAM vortex back into a focused plane wave by the second MS. The transmitting MS (first MS) consists of 60×60 unit cells, while the receiving MS (second MS) comprises 100×100 unit cells, sharing the same structural and electromagnetic characteristics.

of order $\ell = +1$, steered toward $\theta_{\text{scat}} = 30^\circ$ under oblique plane wave illumination at $\theta = 50^\circ$. The phase profile of the MS is designed to simultaneously generate the OAM vortex and steer the scattered wave, resulting in the characteristic “Y”-shaped phase distribution shown in Fig. 4(a). The near-field distributions in Fig. 4(b) and (c) clearly demonstrate the successful generation of the OAM vortex.

In Fig. 5, we demonstrate the transmission and reception of an OAM vortex beam using a two-MS setup. The first MS is illuminated by a plane wave, which transforms it into an OAM vortex beam, steered toward $\theta = 30^\circ$. A second MS, positioned at a distance of 10λ , performs the reverse transformation: it converts the incoming OAM beam back into a plane wave, simultaneously steering it at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and focusing it at a point located $df = 10\lambda$ from the surface. Fig. 5(a) shows the setup cross-section along with the corresponding phase profiles of both MS. The near-field distribution at the intermediate observation plane OP_1 , representing the obliquely directed OAM vortex, is illustrated in Fig. 5(b) and (c). Fig. 5(d) and (e) depict the field at the second observation plane OP_2 , clearly showing the transformation back into a focused plane wave. When the focusing function is removed from the second MS, the scattered field will diverge which would lead to a much wider focal spot on OP_2 .

IV. COMPARISON AND LIMITATIONS

Holographic metasurfaces provide an efficient platform for the generation, de/multiplexing and beam-forming of OAM-carrying signals, simultaneously and concurrently. These emerging communication schemes and the enabling multifunctional devices can be exploited either in smart antennas and next-generation transceivers or as ‘smart scatterers’ in a obstacle-riddled mobile wireless environment [15]. Compared to other similar physical layer schemes, such as array-antennas and relaying, the RIS offer a compromise between performance and efficiency, capitalizing on their ultrathin and compact form-factor, relatively low complexity and consumption,

and rapid electronic reconfigurability. Now, the proposed semi-analytical approach for evaluating the near- and far-field scattering from such holographic RIS, combines physical optics and unit-cell level FWS and thus offers a substantially reduced computational burden compared to full-aperture FWS, with either full structuring or equivalent sheets representation [19], while maintaining higher accuracy compared to simple ray-tracing techniques. Unlike methods that neglect edge effects, shape, or size, this formulation inherently captures diffraction from finite-aperture and arbitrarily shaped surfaces.

Nevertheless, several practical limitations of both the methodology and the employed technology should be acknowledged. Firstly, the physical optics framework as outlined is based on scalar-fields, i.e., ignores vectorial effects and is not valid in scenarios involving strong polarization conversion; this limitation can be easily lifted by extending the scattered field by a vector/dyadic [19]. Secondly, the analysis assumes negligible inter-cell coupling, an approximation that, although valid for the particular unit cell topology studied here, is violated in dense metasurfaces with deeply subwavelength (weakly-confining) cells; homogenization techniques are required to alleviate this limitation. Thirdly, the method can handle arbitrary shape for the scattering surface, not just planar rectangles, provided that it is not (too) concave; in this regard, the main limitation is that the predicted scattered fields are accurate only several wavelengths away from the aperture. Finally, from a technological perspective, the real-world implementation of holographic RIS remains challenging: fabrication imperfections, control/biasing circuitry, and non-idealities in lumped elements (varactors and varistors) will lead to degradation from the performance considered here. Nevertheless, machine learning and other schemes that exploit RIS reconfigurability and self-adaptivity can be used to partially mitigate these problems, e.g., through contemporary FPGA-based controllers that enable dynamic reconfiguration with sub-millisecond latency at relatively low energy cost.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we outline a methodology for calculating the scattered EM field from a finite-aperture MS using physical optics. Additionally, we demonstrate applications of holographic MSs in OAM-based wireless communication scenarios, highlighting the generation of OAM beams from plane waves, and vice-versa, with particular emphasis on oblique incidence and wavefront shaping (steering and focusing). We show results for both forward and reverse transformations, between plane waves and vortex beams, confirming that reconfigurable MS (RIS) are promising components for enabling practical and efficient OAM wireless communication systems. Future prospects of this work include the de/multiplexing of multiple OAM beams depending on their azimuthal order (topological charge).

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